

Jiuge 九歌

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Entry tags: Early Chinese Traditions, Yellow and Yangzi Rivers Region, Hymn, Religious Group, Shamanism, Early Chinese text, Text, Chinese Religion

The Jiuge 九歌 (Nine Songs) is a collection of eleven songs, transmitted as a section of the Chu 楚 poetry collection entitled Chuci 楚辭 (Songs of Chu). It was the Eastern Han 東漢 (25 CE - 220 CE) poet and librarian Wang Yi 王逸 (fl. 130-140 CE) who edited the first Chuci anthology with a commentary, the Chuci zhangju 楚辭章句. A large amount of poems in the collection was attributed to the 4th century BCE Chu state official and poet Qu Yuan 屈原 (340-278 BCE). Both Wang Yi and Liu Xiang 劉向 (79 CE - 8 CE) consider Qu Yuan to be the author of the Jiuge, yet modern scholarship agrees that is highly improbable that he wrote all the songs. Wang Yi, in particular, was the first one to associate this collection to Qu Yuan's name: he believed that the poet wrote the eleven songs after having been banished and having heard rural religious hymns from the south, with the aim of improving their style. His hypothesis has been abandoned in favor of an understanding of the collection as originally meant to be performed at the royal court. Hawkes attributes the Jiuge to one or more poets active at the Chu court in the late Chu capital Shouchun 壽春 (241-223 BCE). The collection mostly consists of shamanic hymns, with the exception of one elegy for fallen soldiers, and a finale, the only two songs which are not dedicated to a god. The titles of the eleven poems are as follows: Donghuang Taiyi 東皇太一 (Taiyi Ruler of the East); Yunzhong jun 雲中君 (The lord within the clouds); Xiang jun 湘君 (The lord of the Xiang river); Xiang furen 湘夫人 (The lady of the Xiang river); Da siming 大司命 (The greater minister of fate); Shao siming 少司命 (The lesser minister of fate); Dong jun 東君 (The lord of the east); Hebo 河伯 (The earl of the river); Shan gui 山鬼 (The mountain spirit); Guo shang 國殤 (The fallen for the state); Li hun 禮魂 (Honoring the souls). It is not known for sure whether the songs included in the collection were originally nine or eleven. Galal Walker attempted to prove that the last two songs, the "Guo shang" and the "Li Hun" have been added at a later time. Yet, various scholars attempted to justify the existence of eleven poems in the collection, instead of nine. For example, the Qing 清 (1636-1912 C.E.) scholar Jiang Ji's 蔣驥 (ca. 1678-1745) theory according to which the "Xiang jun" and "Xiang furen" need to be considered as one piece, as well as the "Da siming" and "Shao siming." The Ming scholar Wang Fuzhi 王夫之 (1619-1692), on the contrary, proposed to read the first and last songs as a prelude and a finale, leaving them out from the count of the nine songs. One other possible explanation is that the title has been chosen to recall the "Nine Songs" from mythological tradition, that appear in texts such as the Shanhai jing 山海經 (Classic of the Mountains and the Seas) and the Da Yumo 大禹謨 chapter of the Shujing 書經 (Classic of Documents). The nine shamanic elegies typically consist of two halves: the first section describes the preparation and the journey in search of a god; the second section usually expresses dismay at the departure of the god or at the fact that the god did not make himself manifest. Some of the songs detail the music, clothing, food, and drink offerings peculiar to the various rituals of invocation of the god. And when the god, usually described with anthropomorphic features, shows up, the relationship he establishes with the shamaness or shaman is of a loving and erotic type. This collection represents a key source of information on shamanic practices in the southern state of Chu, providing us with the names of the worshipped deities, as well as other details on the ritual practices. Unfortunately, we do not have precise information on how these songs were to be performed. As far as it emerges from the texts, the performers of these songs were to be shamans (those able to summon a deity to possess them), dressed in colorful robes and adorned with various kinds of jewelry, and the execution was to be backed by musical accompaniment of various instruments, wind, string, and percussion.

Date Range: 340 BCE - 140 CE

Region: Han empires

Region tags: Asia, East Asia, China

After the short-lived Qin dynasty (221–206 BCE), the Han empires (202 BCE–220 CE) were the second set of polities that ruled over the heartland of present-day China through a unified imperial system. The Liu clan who founded the Western Han (202 BCE–7 CE) emerged from the Chu region along the Yangzi River. Around the beginning of the 1st century CE, an affinal member of the imperial family seized power and founded the Xin Dynasty (9–23 CE). After a period of civil strife, a distant member of the Liu clan eventually founded the Eastern Han (25–220) that reunified the empire. The seat of the imperial house was moved from the western capital of Chang'an (modern-day Xi'an) to the eastern capital Luoyang.

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Chuci buzhu 楚辭補注 (ed. Hong Xingzu 洪興祖) (1983). Peking: Zhonghua Shuju.
- Source 2: Chuci jinzhushu 楚辭今注 (eds. Tang Bingzheng 湯炳正 et al.) (1996). Shanghai: Shanghai Guji.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://ctext.org/chu-ci/jiu-ge>

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

- Source 1 URL: <https://ctext.org/chu-ci/jiu-ge>

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Written

↳ Inked
–with Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Paper

↳ Specify type of paper
– Specify: not a specific kind of paper

– Bamboo

Notes: The text, as most literary texts at the time, was likely originally written on bamboo slips.

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

–Other [specify]: no

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

–Other [specify]: no

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– No

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Modern scholarship believes that the songs that are part of the collection were originally conceived to be performed at court in Chu. More specifically, Hawkes holds that the author or authors

were active at the court of the capital Shouchun 壽春 (241-223 BCE).

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Notes: The eleven songs that constitute the collection were probably performed during shamanic rituals. The performance was probably carried out to the accompaniment of dances and various string, wind, and percussion musical instruments.

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– Field doesn't know

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– Yes

↳ Is it orally recited?

– Yes

↳ Is there any particular affect of the oral recitation of the text?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is it read?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Describe the nature of the ritual practice?

– Specify: The songs describe the food and drink offerings, the robes and the jewelry worn by the shamans during the rituals, the scents spread in the ritual hall, and various details of the ceremonies.

↳ Is the text employed in large scale rituals?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the text employed in small scale rituals?

– Field doesn't know

↳ How often do the rituals take place?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks?

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?

– No

↳ Are there synchronic practices?

– Yes

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The songs refer to various kinds of herbs used during the rituals, but it is unclear whether these herbs were intoxicants. Explicit references are made to their fragrant smell, but no explicit reference is made to their possible function as healing or intoxicating drugs. Traditionally, shamanic rituals in ancient China were associated with the use of medicinal herbs.

↳ Are there other substances (such as food or drink, for example) that are consumed during rituals?

– Yes

Notes: The various songs refer to a huge variety of meat, grains, and drinks that are prepared for the ritual, in order to invoke the deity.

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

Notes: The Jiuge are part of the poetry collection entitled Chuci 楚辭. The received edition of the Chuci, edited during the 12th century CE under the title Chuci buzhu 楚辭補注, displays significant differences in the sequence of the chapters if compared with Wang Yi's 王逸 Chuci zhangju 楚辭章句 (2nd century CE) and the Chuci shiwen 楚辭釋文 (compiled before the Southern Tang). Wang Yi, in his commentary, claims to refer to a previous edition of the anthology, edited by Liu Xiang 劉向. It is possible that, at an early stage, the text circulated in the form of a bamboo manuscript.

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– Yes

↳ If multiple versions are proper, is there a differentiation among versions by any means?

– Yes

↳ Age of extant version of text?

– Yes

↳ Content of text?

– No

↳ Ritual purpose of text?

– No

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Yes

Notes: The Jiuge are part of the Chuci 楚辭 ("Songs of Chu") collection of southern verses, attributed to Qu Yuan 屈原 and various authors from the state of Chu 楚.

↳ Is there a sense of canonization?

– No

↳ Is the text part of a series of volumes?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

Notes: The Jiuge, together with the Tian wen 天問, the Lisao 離騷, and other poems ascribed to Qu Yuan 屈原 that are part of the Chuci 楚辭 collection, are considered the seminal work of the literary genre of the Chu poetry (Chuci). Subsequently, also Han-era poets contributed to the genre of the Chuci. For instance, Wang Yi 王逸, editor of the Chuci Zhangju 楚辭章句, in which he also included some of his poems. The Chuci in general have been influential on classical Chinese poetry for centuries, for example on the work of poets such as Jia Yi 賈誼, Du Fu 杜甫, and Han Yu 韓愈, and became subject of study for many scholars, receiving several commentaries.

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

↳ Behavioral literature?

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: The southern genre of the Chuci became a relevant literary genre on its own right.

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Other [specify]: None of the previous

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Notes: The songs do not formulate a religious calendar, but display explicit reference to the specific days in which the rituals are to be performed.

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: In the last two songs of the collection, both the term hun 魂 and the term po 魄 appear, respectively in the title of the last song of the collection (Li hun 禮魂), and in the compound hunpo 魂魄 in the last verse of the penultimate poem, entitled Guo shang 國殤. Both terms refer back to the concept of soul. Traditionally, ancient Chinese religion envisions a form of dualism in the conception of the human soul: a non-corporeal, spiritual soul, called hun, and a corporeal soul, closely connected to the body, even after death, called po.

↳ Spirit-Mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other parts?

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body?

– Yes

↳ Other spirit-body relationship?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Within conceptions of the mind: are there distinct notions of psychological states or aggregates?

– No

↳ Do practitioners engage in debates about mind-body dualism?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are debates framed in other ways?

– No

↳ Do practitioners distinguish between a corporeal body and an incorporeal soul or spirit?

– Yes

↳ Are there other sides or features of the debate?

– Field doesn't know

↳ What are historical mainstream and minority positions?

– Field doesn't know

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

Notes: The songs in the Jiuge do not specify the spatial location of the afterlife. Some of the songs mention the places in which the deities reside (both places on earth, such as mountains and rivers, and celestial places). In other poems from the Chuci collection, the souls of deceased people are able to wander through these places.

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– Yes

↳ Do these practices take place at tombs/burial sites?

– No

↳ Do these practices take place for the veneration OR worship of the dead?

– Yes

Notes: The last song in the Jiuge collection is entitled Li Hun 禮魂 ("Honoring the souls") and it describes a ritual for the worship of deceased humans. The previous song, entitled Guo Shang 國殤 ("The fallen for the state") is focused on the deceased soldiers that become heroes in the afterlife.

↳ For the worship of a deceased person(s)?

– Yes

↳ For the worship of a deified human?

– No

↳ For the worship of a deceased hero?

– Yes

↳ For the veneration of a deceased person(s)?

– No

↳ For the veneration of a deified human?

– No

↳ For the veneration of a deceased hero?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Some scholars believe that the deity to which the first song in the collection is dedicated, Taiyi 太一, was the chief celestial god. The cult of Taiyi was present both in Chu and

in Qi, and his cult was also established during the Han, beginning in 113 B.C. as a state sacrifice during the reign of Emperor Wu.

Previously human spirits are present

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt

– Field doesn't know

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The songs in the Jiuge do not specify whether previously human spirits (protagonists of the last two songs in the collection) have knowledge of this world.

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits have memory of life

– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living

– Field doesn't know

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

– Yes

Notes: At least the shaman is able to see the deities.

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– Yes

Notes: They can be physically felt at least by the shaman.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– Field doesn't know

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– Field doesn't know

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– Field doesn't know

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– Field doesn't know

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Field doesn't know

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Field doesn't know

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– Field doesn't know

↳ Know basic character (personal essence)

– Field doesn't know

↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The deity Siming 司命, at least, appears to know the allotted life-span for each human being.

↳ Have other knowledge of this world

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

Notes: One example is the god Siming 司命, who is responsible for deciding humans' life-span.

↳ Supernatural beings can reward

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can punish

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life?

– No

↳ In dreams?

– No

↳ In trance possession?

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices?

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists?

– Yes

↳ Only through monarch?

– No

↳ Other?

– Specify: The deities possess the shamans that invoke them.

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– Field doesn't know

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion

– Yes

Notes: The deities are described as joyful as a consequence of the offerings they receive.

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature

– Specify: The deities in the poems entertain love-like relationships with the shamans.

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model?

– No

↳ Organized hierarchically?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The collection does not explicitly define a hierarchy, but many scholars believe that Taiyi 太一 from the Donghuang Taiyi 東皇太一 (the first poem of the collection) is a chief deity.

↳ Power of beings is domain specific?

– Yes

Notes: Some of the deities are strictly related to a place, as for example a specific river, or a specific mountain.

↳ Other organization of pantheon?

– Specify: The organization of the pantheon is not defined in the songs.

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is unknown whether the songs were actually performed as a form of invocation for the deities during the rituals.

Are other categories of beings present?

–Other [specify]: none.

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Notes: The text does not guide divination practices, but some form of divination appear to be implied, as for example in the opening line of the first song, Donghuang Taiyi 東皇太一, in which the focus is put on the luck of the day chosen for the ritual.

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– No

Notes: The songs do not specifically delve into the topic of supernatural monitoring, being more specifically focused on the perspective of the shamans, who receive the deity and later, after an almost amorous encounter, suffer from separation.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Notes: The deities in the text do not explicitly mete out either punishments or rewards, even if they are deities capable of punishing and rewarding men. Punishments and rewards, however, are not the focus of the poetry collection.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Notes: The deities in the text do not explicitly mete out either punishments or rewards, even if they are deities capable of punishing and rewarding men. Punishments and rewards, however, are not the focus of the poetry collection.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– No

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Notes: The songs do not explicitly require celibacy, but there is a case in which celibacy might be implied. The song entitled Hebo 河伯 ("The earl of the river") is dedicated to the only well-known deity that appears in the collection. The text possibly refers to the ancient tradition of offering a virgin as a human sacrifice to the Yellow River. Human sacrifices to the river are attested already from Shang oracle bone inscriptions. The virgin was placed on a raft that was supposed to break offshore so that the young girl would drown in the river.

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Notes: The songs do not explicitly require human sacrifice, but the song entitled Hebo 河伯 ("The earl of the river") possibly refers to the ancient tradition of offering a virgin as a human sacrifice to the Yellow River. Human sacrifices to the river are attested already from Shang oracle bone inscriptions. The virgin was placed on a raft that was supposed to break offshore so that the young girl would drown in the river.

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– Yes

Notes: The songs display several valuable objects, precious stones, and jewels that are offered to the deities.

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Notes: The text describes the preparation for and the execution of shamanic invocation rituals, but it does not prescribe the participation to such rituals. The songs making up the collection were probably sung during the rituals.

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Notes: The text describes the preparation for and the execution of shamanic invocation rituals, but it does not prescribe the participation to such rituals. The songs making up the collection were probably sung during the rituals.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– Yes

↳ Are sacrifices specified by the text?

– Yes

↳ Animal sacrifice?

– Yes

Notes: The songs refer to various meat offerings.

↳ Human sacrifice?

– No

Notes: The songs do not explicitly require human sacrifice, but the song entitled Hebo 河伯 ("The earl of the river") possibly refers to the ancient tradition of offering a virgin as a human sacrifice to the Yellow River. Human sacrifices to the river are attested already from Shang oracle bone inscriptions. The virgin was placed on a raft that was supposed to break offshore so that the young girl would drown in the river.

↳ Are there self-sacrifices specified by the text?

– No

↳ Are there material offerings present?

– Yes

↳ Are they mandatory?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are they composed of valuable objects?

– Yes

↳ Are they composed of daily-life objects?

– No

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches)?

– No

↳ Are there particular smells associated with material offerings?

– Yes

Notes: Various songs refer to herbs and flowers' smell and to the fragrant smell of food offerings.

↳ Are there particular visual stimuli (colors, symbols) associated with the offerings? (I.e. 'must be bright' 'must include red')

– Yes

Notes: The songs have multiple references to colors, especially related to the description of flowers and clothes.

↳ Other?

– *Specify:* Material offerings mostly include food (especially meat), spicy drinks, flowers, and precious jewels.

↳ Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory?

– No

↳ Is the maintenance of the place regulated by the text?

– No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– A state

Notes: The shamanic cult described in the songs pertaining to the Jiuge collection is connected to the southern state of Chu during the Warring States period (475–221 BCE).

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– Other

Notes: Field doesn't know.

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Notes: None.

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– No

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– Yes

Notes: Education had been primarily restricted to males for centuries. It should be noted, however, that within this text and in the Chu state tradition to which the text refers, at this stage in history, the role of summoning deities was mostly reserved to female shamanesses. Early Chinese has two different words to distinguish between female shamaness and male shaman, that are, respectively, wu 巫 and xi 覡. Within the Jiuge however, the most frequently recurring term related to the shaman, according to Wang Yi's interpretation of the text, is ling 靈.

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– Yes

Notes: There is a reference to warfare in the next-to-last song of the collection, which is dedicated to the soldiers who died fighting for the state and whose souls became heroes in the afterlife.

↳ Does the text dictate how to control an institutionalized military?

– No

↳ Does the text restrict/advocate for participation in exogenous military organizations?

– No

↳ Does the text celebrate/bemoan protection/subjugation by an exogenous military force?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

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General References

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